

THE DEATH OF ATOMS AND THE NEW CHEMISTRY IN TERMS OF WORLDVIEW 'THE IDION'

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Abstract: The worldview THE IDION brings modifications to the established chemistry, the one it accepts. And he accepts chemistry mainly built up to 1900 AD.

He considers that the few indivisible parts of matter are the bubbles of the ether that have mass and charge and make up the atoms. Perhaps these are eternal, but individuals end up in a long time in these bubbles. Again, in combustion at high temperature, some of the reactant elements, the atoms of the reactants end up in bubbles of which they are composed.

Water in our theory consists of three bubbles and one oxygen atom, and the three bubbles of atoms, joined by hydrogen atoms from the (6 atoms, 12 bubbles) that form the oxygen atom at the peaks of a normal icosahedron, form an angle highlighted in radiation diffraction experiments, in ice crystals.

All complex atoms consist of hydrogen atoms and these consist of two ether bubbles. Deuterium and tritium are atoms of three and four bubbles, orbiting in a circle, as we have indicated for the two of the hydrogen atom

Keywords: worldview THE IDION, oxygen atom, hydrogen atoms.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to the worldview¹, atoms of elements consist of bubbles of thinner ether, floating in the continuously denser ether. Bubbles have charge and mass, and in my work THE NEW PHYSICS WITHOUT THE CONCEPT OF ELECTRIC CHARGE² I showed that a bubble has a mass of about 3.66×10^{-32} kgr to the hydrogen atom with a constant kinetic energy equal to the potential. If the rotational speed of the two bubbles decreases due to ether resistance, then with the same constant kinetic energy, but at a slower speed than before, we arrive at the mass of the two grains of the hydrogen atom $m = 1.91 \times 10^{-27}$ kgr each grain, that is, close to the mass predicted by established physics for the proton and for the hydrogen atom.

The atomic scientists formulated that matter consists of atoms, following Democritus. Democritus set as a principle the complete and the empty, and the complete consists of indivisible minimum parts of matter, the atoms. These are eternal and unchanging, they have no end of existence, and this was accepted by Dalton who formulated the atomic theory more recently.

We will question the eternity of the atoms and argue that they die, end up in an astonishingly long time and that many are killed, many end up in cremation.

2. METHODOLOGY

The work here is a continuation of the worldview TO IDION and as there, it has the same principles. The principles, as Aristotle says in LECTURE ON NATURE and ON SOUL, are the acceptances of the philosophers, on which their theory is built. Although the bubbles of the ether are the result of the development of the worldview, here they are also taken as a principle to which matter is subject. And these are few and indivisible, the atoms of Democritus.

¹ THE TOTAL THEORY International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, vol 8 Issue 1 Apr 2020- Sept2020, THE TOTAL THEORY II, vol 9 Issue 2 Oct 2021- Mar 2022

² International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, vol 12 Issue 1 Apr 2024- Sept 2024

At the same time, deductive reasoning was used for the elaboration of the thesis, in which the inductive method and the abductive method are incorporated.

Invention is a basic method of work. In other words, the fate of atoms was invented, as in every being.

THE NON-ETERNITY OF ATOMS

As I have shown in my successive papers in atomic physics, atoms have electric-magnetic potential energy and kinetics. I gave them as constants. But these actions, multiplied by a series of numbers, the sum of which equals the unit, is invented. The order (series) is,

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{16} + \dots = 1$$

And the energy of the atom is, $E = E_0 \cdot \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n}$

But however, we considered that in matter there are little indivisible, the bubbles that have charge and mass and of which atoms are composed. Then in the same way, the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^n} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{16} + \dots$, somewhere in a minimal term ends up and is not infinite so that its sum is a unit, but is very little less than a unit. It is, $\sum_{n=1}^k \frac{1}{2^n} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{16} + \dots + \frac{1}{2^k}$, where k is very large but finite.

In our work we have shown that the hydrogen atom, where the bubbles-particles orbit about center of mass, consumes electrical power and at the same time consumes kinetic and dynamic power. Then the energy of the atom is constantly renewed from zero, from where it takes it, but a little less than before each time, because the (series) order in which the energy multiplies, is not infinite. Thus, in the long run the lack of energy accumulates and ends up in the death of the atoms, it breaks down into the bubbles, which are the indivisible and perhaps the eternal and unchanging bodies.

THE HYDROGEN ATOM IS MONOATOMIC WEIGHT 1 AND OXYGEN WEIGHT 12

Berzelius found that the weight of hydrogen in water is 1/8 of the weight of oxygen. He got one device as in shape.

Σχ. 16.5. Εύρεση της κατά βάρους συστάσεως με σύνθεση.

In a horizontal tube, he put CuO that weighed it. The tube continued into a U-shaped tube, where there was weighed hygroscopic substance CaCl₂. It heated the tube containing CuO and blew hydrogen into the tube. The oxygen of CuO with hydrogen under the heat submitted, formed water,

and receiving water absorption by CaCl₂. In the first tube remained CuO and Cu, which weighed and weighed and CaCl₂ which was watered with water and calculated the weight of the water. He also calculated the oxygen weight of the water from the difference between the original CuO and CuO+Cu remaining after the experiment. He found a hydrogen-to-oxygen weight ratio of 1/8, if the water is H₂O.

But we maintain that in heating and combustion atoms are killed, end up and turn into the sum of the bubbles-particles of which they are composed.

Hydrogen, for us, is a monoatomic gas. And when oxygen is burned in hydrogen, in an airtight flask, the following reaction occurs:

The symbol ↑ means that the atoms ended up in bubbles, and the water is three hydrogen atoms, with one oxygen atom, H₃O.

In Berzelius' experiment the bubbles formed by the hydrogen, copper and oxygen atoms that ended up, were carried away by the water vapor and were present in the mixture of CaCl₂ and water.

So, if he took 18 grams of water and found that 2 grams was H₂ in the water, it was actually H₃, that is, three hydrogen atoms. $\frac{2}{3} = 0.66666$, $3 = (2/0.66666)$ gr, one hydrogen then is 0.66666 gr than has been calculated in water. And the oxygen that after removal was 16 gr, that is, the weight of O, that removed the remaining Cu+CuO from the original CuO was 16 gr. But, in the reaction we gave, there are an O atom in the water and an O atom that ended up in bubbles and that were in the water. So, at 16 gr, there are one O atom in water and one O in bubbles, i.e. from 8 gr. His atom's weight after combustion was in water (O)/0.6666=8/0.66666=12 atomic weights. Thus, the oxygen atom O has an atomic weight of 12 atomic weights of hydrogen.

Lavoisier had weighed oxygen and hydrogen before combustion and found a weight-to-oxygen ratio of 1/6. He was accused of not having accurate weights at that time and therefore did not find the 1/8 ratio that Berzelius later found. But we recall that hydrogen is a monoatomic gas, while Lavoisier considered it diatomic its volume that reacted with oxygen, that is, it had two H atoms, so the two monoatomic ones are $2 \times 6 = 12$ atomic weights (12, close to what we calculated (12). In other words, his weights were extremely expensive.

In the production of water, from hydrogen and oxygen in the presence of fire or electric spark in an airtight flask, the volumes of hydrogen are two and one of the oxygen that react. But after accepting our own analysis, monoatomic hydrogen occupies half the volume of the corresponding oxygen O₂. That is, the number of Avogadro is half in hydrogen relative to the volume of oxygen. Then multiply $2 \times 6 = 12$ the weight of H, because the volume of an H is half the volume of O₂ while the 2H, (H₂) as much as the volume of oxygen, and Lavoisier found 1:6, H₂ :O₂ because he used as reactants, two volumes of H₂ (=1H) and one O.

THE PRINCIPLE OF INCORRUPTIBILITY OF MATTER

In various experiments and by combustion, Lavoisier weighed before the reacting elements or chemical compounds and then weighed the airtight flask in which the reactions took place and the products were obtained. He found that weight is conserved and formulated that matter is transformed in its reactions, but is conserved. He formulated the principle of preservation-indestructibility of matter.

But we argued that in combustion atoms end up in the bubbles-particles that are composed, so the principle of indestructibility is generalized and includes bubbles.

THE ATOMIC WEIGHT OF MAGNESIUM Mg

Mg was considered by established chemistry to have the atomic weight of 24, which is the same as the O₂ that we found.

If we heat MgO to 2000 degrees Celsius, with carbon C, we get,

According to established chemistry³, that's what we get. For us, however, the reaction occurs with the following products,

The products, because CO is a gas, were captured in an airtight bottle, where the reactants were weighed and then the products. The bubbles of $\frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$ and C were carried away by CO and of Mg↑ by Mg.

We consider that the reactants (2MgO+ 2C), have a weight according to the given science $2 \times (24+16) + (2 \times 12) = 104$. Then the products (Mg + CO + Mg ↑ + $\frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2$ ↑ + C↑), have weight with the atomic weights we found and the weight of carbon we will find C=24,

$$2(24+16)+12+24=116= 2\text{Mg} + (24+12)+12+24= 2\text{Mg}+72$$

and Mg=22 atomic weights of hydrogen H.

³ ELEMENTS OF INORGANIC CHEMISTRY, Manolkidis-Beza, p. 353

And Cl is monoatomic, like hydrogen H. MgCl occurs naturally in crystals with water (MgCl₂ for established chemistry). At high temperature⁴, MgCl₂ melts in a solution of water, and evaporatively decomposes. The established chemistry, gives the reaction,

We give the reaction,

As you notice, the magnesium in the products that ended up in bubbles, is monoatomic.

THE ATOMIC WEIGHT OF CARBON

When methane is burned in an oxygen environment, the established chemistry receives the reaction,

We accept the reaction,

If the reactants had a weight according to established science, $2 \times (12+4) + (3 \times (2 \times 16))$ i.e. $(2\text{CH}_4 + 3\text{O}_2) = 128$, then the products are according to us, $\text{CO}_2 + \text{C}\uparrow + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2\uparrow + 2\text{H}$,

$$128 = \text{C} + (2 \times 12) + \text{C} + (2 \times (3 + 12)) + (2 \times 12) + (2 \times 1) = 2\text{C} + 80$$

So $\text{C} = 24$ atomic weights of hydrogen.

As we indicated that the volume of O₂ is twice that of H, here the volume of CH₄ is 1.5 times that of oxygen O₂ and three times that of H ($2 \times 1.5 = 3$), and the number NA for the hydrogen atom is divided by 2 and 1.5 for the oxygen and methane atom.

Carbon and oxygen bubbles after combustion are carried away by carbon dioxide, not water vapor.

THE WEIGHT OF NITROGEN

We found that the atomic weight of oxygen is 12 atomic weights of hydrogen. Let's now find nitrogen.

When we burn nitrogen in the presence of oxygen at a suitable temperature and pressure, we get according to established science⁵,

We support the reaction.

Like oxygen with hydrogen $\text{O}_2 + 4\text{H} \rightarrow \text{OH}_3 + \text{H}\uparrow + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_2\uparrow$

If the reactants ($\text{N}_2 + 4\text{H}$) are weighing $2 \times 14 + 4 = 32$ according to established science, then the products according to us are, $\text{N} + 3 + 1 + \text{N} = 32$, and $\text{N} = 14$ atomic weights of hydrogen.

But the mole volume of nitrogen is $4/2 = 2$ of hydrogen H, since in the initial reaction, they got a $4/2$ ratio of volumes of hydrogen H₂ to nitrogen N₂. In other words, it is the ratio of the mole volume of nitrogen to oxygen is equal.

THE WEIGHT OF SULFUR S

Hydrogen sulfide burns with oxygen according to us, such as,

While mainstream science, gives the cremation,

⁴ ELEMENTS OF INORGANIC CHEMISTRY, Zegeli 1909, p. 343

⁵ ELEMENTS OF INORGANIC CHEMISTRY, p. 294

According to established science, the burdens of the reactants are,

With product weights, $100 = (3+12) + 2S + 1 + 12 = 28 + 2S$

So the atomic weight of S is 36.

EPILOGUE

The worldview THE IDION brings modifications to the established chemistry, the one it accepts. And he accepts chemistry mainly built up to 1900 AD.

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